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Research Article

Green Tea Catechins-Based Herbal Churna: A Novel Approach for Alzheimer's Disease Treatment

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ABSTRACT

In the long struggle to overcome the powerful forces of nature, the human beings have always turned towards plants for food, shelter, clothing, and healing. Even today herbal medicine plays an important role in the management of diseases. Though we are in 21st century where modern technology and scientific discoveries are ushering remarkable changes in our lives, nevertheless, the story of plants as herbal medicines definitely continues to unfold, however, quietly and independently. Synthetic drugs are being prepared by keeping the natural drugs as standards but the efficacy of the herbal drugs cannot be imitated & hence 80% of the world population rely on natural drugs for treating their ailments. Ayurvedic science has got its rich heritage in India. People in India believe that natural products are safe compared to synthetic drugs. Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a neurodegenerative disorder and the most common form of dementia characterized by cognitive and memory impairment. One of the mechanisms involved in the pathogenesis of AD, is the oxidative stress being involved in AD 's development and progression. Catechins flavonoids are contained in green tea extract (GTE) and are defined as the active components of green tea, accounting for its therapeutic properties.

INTRODUCTION

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is one of the most common neurodegenerative disorders Worldwide. Its incidence is gradually increasing because of an aging demographic. Therefore, AD prevention and modification is important to improve the health status of older adults. Over 100 years ago, the first case of Alzheimer's disease (AD) was reported by

Dr. Alois Alzheimer, In a German woman, Auguste Deter. It was subsequently named "Alzheimer's disease" by Dr. Emil Kraepelin and colleagues [1,4]. The number of individuals with AD is gradually increasing due to worldwide Aging. Catechins, which are bioactive components of tea, have antioxidative and anti-inflammatory effects. Moreover, other potential properties

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related to AD prevention and modification have been reported in in vitro and in vivo studies. Green tea catechins, particularly epigallocatechin gallate (EGCG), have emerged as promising Natural compounds with neuroprotective properties. Catechins are polyphenolic antioxidants found in *Camellia sinensis* that exhibit anti-amyloidogenic, anti-inflammatory, and synaptic protective Effects. Studies suggest that EGCG can reduce A β aggregation, inhibit tau hyperphosphorylation, modulate oxidative stress, and enhance cognitive function.

➤ Green Tea Catechins

➤ Plant Description:

1. Type: Evergreen shrub or small tree
2. Height: Typically pruned to 3-5 feet for harvesting, but can grow up to 15-20 feet in the wild
3. Leaves: Glossy, dark green, serrated edges; young leaves and buds are harvested for tea
4. Flowers: Small, white, fragrant flowers with yellow stamens; bloom in autumn
5. Fruit: Small, round capsules with one to three seeds
6. Class and Category:

Class: Flavonoids (subcategory: flavan-3-ols or catechins)

Category: Polyphenolic Compounds (Antioxidants)

7. Chemical Composition: Green tea is particularly rich in catechins, the most abundant being epigallocatechin-3-Gallate (EGCG), along with other flavonoids and caffeine[12,14].

8. Sources and Variants: Green tea is minimally processed compared to black or oolong tea, preserving higher concentrations of catechins. Major regions producing green tea include China, Japan, India, and Sri Lanka .

□ Green Tea Catechins In The Treatment Of Alzheimer's Disease

1. Antioxidant Effects
2. Anti-amyloid Properties
3. Anti-inflammatory Effects
4. Chelation of Metal Ions
5. Signaling
6. Improvement in Cognitive Function

Fig No 1. Green Tea

Fig No. 2 Several Uses of Green Tea Catechins

1.2 Herbal Churna

Herbal Churna (or Churnas) are finely powdered formulations of medicinal herbs used in traditional systems like Ayurveda. Prepared by cleaning, drying, pulverizing, and sieving herbs, churnas are effective due to their small particle size, which enhances absorption and bioavailability. They are natural, safe, customizable, cost-effective, and easy to use. An example is Green Tea Catechins Herbal Churna, which combines green tea polyphenols with other herbs to provide potent antioxidant effects, support weight management, improve cardiovascular and brain health, and boost immunity. These formulations are increasingly being made into tablets for precise dosing and modern convenience.

Fig No 3. Preparation of Herbal Churna

➤ Alzheimer's Disease

Over 100 years ago, the first case of Alzheimer's disease (AD) was reported by Dr. Alois Alzheimer, in a German woman, Auguste Deter. It was subsequently named "Alzheimer's Disease" By Dr. Emil Kraepelin and colleagues. The number of individuals with AD is gradually increasing due to worldwide aging. [1,2,3,4]. Alzheimer's disease is a progressive neurological disorder that affects memory, thinking, and behavior.

Fig No 4. Difference of Healthy Brain and Alzheimer's Brain

A. Symptoms of Alzheimer's Disease

1. Memory Loss
2. Difficulty in Problem-Solving and Planning
3. Confusion with Time and Place
4. Difficulty in Completing Familiar Tasks
5. Difficulty in Understanding Visual and Spatial Relationships
6. Language Problems

7. Misplacing Things and Losing the Ability to Retrace Steps
8. Decreased or Poor Judgment
9. Withdrawal from Work or Social Activities

➤ Pathophysiology of Alzheimer's Disease

Its pathophysiology involves complex interactions between genetic, molecular, and environmental factors, leading to the characteristic features of amyloid plaques, neurofibrillary tangles, and widespread neuronal loss [1].

Fig No 5. Pathophysiology of Alzheimer's Disease

Plant Profile:

Common name: Green tea plant
Scientific name: *Camellia sinensis*
Family: Theaceae

Fig No 6. Green Tea Catechins Powder

- Green tea catechins, especially EGCG, are powerful antioxidants with multiple health
- Benefits They support weight loss, heart health, and brain function, and may help
- Prevent cancer. Catechins also have anti-inflammatory, anti-aging, and blood sugar-

Common name: Bramhi, Water hyssop
Scientific name: *Bacopa monnieri*
Family: Plantaginaceae

1.Green Tea:

Chemical constituents: catechin
Polyphenols, Alkaloids
Amino acids, Vitamins, Minerals

- Regulating properties, making them popular in both health supplements and skincare.

Fig No 7. Chem. Str. Of Green Tea Catechins

Bramhi:

Chemical constituents: Bacosides
Alkaloids Saponins
Flavonoids Sterols

Fig No 8. Bramhi Powder

Brahmi is a traditional Ayurvedic herb known for boosting brain function. It enhances memory, focus, and mental clarity, and helps reduce stress and anxiety. It also has antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties, supports skin and hair health, and may aid in managing neurological conditions [27, 28].

Fig No 9. Chem. Str. of Bramhi

3. Ashwagandha:

<p>Common name: Ashwagandha</p> <p>Indian ginseng</p> <p>Scientific name: <i>Withania somnifera</i></p> <p>Family: Solanaceae</p>	<p>Chemical constituents: Withanolides</p> <p>Alkaloids</p> <p>Flavonoids</p> <p>Iron</p>
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Fig No 10. Ashwagandha Powder

Ashwagandha is a powerful adaptogen with wide-ranging benefits, including reducing stress and anxiety, boosting energy, improving sleep, enhancing cognitive function, and supporting the immune system. It also helps in hormonal balance and muscle recovery [34,35].

Fig No 11. Chem. Str. of Ashwagandha

4. Shankpushpi:

Common name: Shankpushpi Morning glory Scientific name: Convolvulus pluricaulis Family: Convolvulaceae	Chemical constituents: Alkaloids Flavonoids Glycoside Coumarins Sterols Volatile oils
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Fig No 12. Shankpushpi Powder

Shankpushpi is a brain and nervous system tonic that helps with memory, focus, and reducing stress. It also aids in improving sleep, supports immunity, and has anti-inflammatory benefits [9,10].

Fig No 13. Chem. Str. of Shankpushpi

5. Turmeric:

Common name: Turmeric
Haldi, Indian saffron
Scientific name: *Curcuma longa*
Family: Zingiberaceae

Chemical constituents: Curcuminoids
Curcumin, Volatile Oils
Polyphenols Resins

Fig No 14. Turmeric Powder

Turmeric is a potent anti-inflammatory and antioxidant herb with numerous health benefits, including supporting joint, heart, and brain health, improving digestion, and promoting healthy skin. Its active compound, curcumin, is central to its therapeutic properties[5,7].

Fig No 15. Chem. Str. of Turmeric

6. Gotu Kola:

Common name: Gotu Kola
Mandukaparni
Scientific name: *Centella asiatica*
Family: Umbelliferae

Chemical constituents: Triterpenoids
Flavonoids
Polyphenols
Volatile oils Amino acids

Fig No 16. Gotu Kola Powder

Gotu Kola is a versatile herb known for its benefits in improving cognitive function, supporting skin health, reducing anxiety, and promoting circulation. It also aids in wound healing and has anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties [12,16,24].

Fig No 17. Chem. Str. of Gotu Kola

7.Black pepper:

Common name: Black Pepper
Peppercorn Kali Mirch
Scientific name: Piper nigrum
Family: Piperaceae

Chemical constituents: Piperine
Chavicine
Essential oils
Volatile oils

Fig No 18. Black Pepper Powder

Black pepper is more than just a spice; it's a powerful medicinal herb with anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and digestive benefits. It helps enhance nutrient absorption, promotes digestion, supports the immune system, and has potential weight-loss benefits [29].

Fig No 19. Chem. Str. Of Black Pepper

➤ MATERIAL AND METHOD

Materials:

Collection of green tea leaves and other herbs required for formulation of herbal churn. Herbs are as follows; Green tea extract, Bramhi, Ashwagandha, Shankpushpi, turmeric, Gotu kola, Black pepper [14,15].

Table No 1. Materials Used

Sr No	Herbs	Category
1.	Green tea extract	Antioxidants, protect brain cells and Reduces plaques
2.	Bramhi	Cognitive enhancement, Stress relief and Reduce anxiety.
3.	Ashwagandha	Reduce stress and Support neuronal regeneration.
4.	Shankpushpi	Brain function, Memory and Calming agent
5.	Turmeric	Anti-inflammatory and Antioxidants
6.	Gotu Kola	Cognitive function and Improve circulation.
7.	Black pepper	Enhance absorption

Method:

☐ Extraction of Catechins from Green Tea Leaves by Maceration

To extract catechins, especially EGCG (epigallocatechin gallate), from green tea leaves using the maceration method. A method for

preparing green tea catechins using the maceration process, which is a simple and widely used extraction technique [30,32].

Fig. No 20. Maceration Process

➤ Method of preparation of herbal churna

• Method of Preparation of Herbal Churna

- Green tea extract preparation
- Dry and grind them into a fine powder
- Obtain dried powder of bramhi ashwagandha, turmeric, gotu kola.
- Mix in a specific ratio to optimize neuroprotection
- Add black pepper extract to boost absorption
- Ensure uniform mixing for consistent therapeutic effect
- The desired herbal churn is obtained by grinding and mixing method
- To evaluate prepared herbal churn in various methods

➤ Formulation of Herbal Churna

Table No 2. Formulation Table

Sr. No.	Herbs	Standard proportion (%)	Working quantity (gm)
1.	Green tea catechins	20%	10gm
2.	Bramhi	15%	7.5gm

3.	Ashwagandha	15%	7.5gm
4.	Shankhpushpi	15%	7.5gm
5.	Gotu Kola	15%	7.5gm
6.	Turmeric	10%	5gm
7.	Black pepper	10%	5gm
8.	Total	100%	50gm

➤ **Evaluation Parameters**

1.Organoleptic Characteristics

1.Color:

Churna was taken into watch glass and placed against white background in white tube light .

It was observed for their color by naked eye.

2.Odor:

gram churna was smelled and odour was noted.

3.Taste:

A Pinch of churna was taken and examined for its taste buds of the tongue. [4,5].

2.Physicochemical Parameters

1.Determination of PH:

Fig No 21. pH Test

Determination of Loss on Drying:

Calculate the loss on drying using the formula:

$$\% \text{ Loss on drying} = (W_2 - W_3) / (W_2 - W_1) \times 100$$

Where:

W₁ = Weight of empty Petridish

W₂ = Weight of Petridish + Sample before drying

W₃ = Final constant weight after drying

Given: W₁ = 50gm, W₂ = 52gm, W₃ = 51.82gm

$$\% \text{ Loss on drying} = 52 - 51.82 / 52 - 50 \times 100$$

$$= 0.18 / 2 \times 100 = 9.00 \% \text{ w / w}$$

Fig No 22. Loss on Drying

3. Determination of Ash value:

1. Total Ash Value:

Calculate the total ash value in mg/g of the air-dried material using the formula:

$$\% \text{ Total Ash Value} = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times 1000$$

Where: W_1 = Weight of empty Petridish

$$W_2 = \text{Weight of Petridish} + \text{Ash}$$

Given: $W_1 = 50\text{gm}$, $W_2 = 50.065$, Sample weight = 2gm

$$\% \text{ Total Ash Value} = \frac{50.065 - 50}{2} \times 1000$$

$$= \frac{0.065}{2} \times 1000 = 32.5 \text{ mg/g}$$

Fig No 23. Total Ash Value

2. Acid Insoluble Ash Value:

Calculate the acid-insoluble ash value (mg/g) using the formula:

$$\% \text{ Acid insoluble Ash Value} = \frac{\text{Acid insoluble Ash Weight}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times 100$$

Given: Weight of sample taken = 2g

Weight of empty petri dish = 50 g

Weight of petri dish + acid-insoluble ash = 50.130 g

Weight of residue (ash) = 50.130 – 50 = 0.130

% Acid insoluble Ash Value = $0.130 / 2 \times 100 = 6.5 \%$

3. Determination of Extractive values:

1. Water Soluble Extractive Value

% Water soluble extractive value = $\frac{\text{Initial mass} - \text{Mass of water extraction residue}}{\text{initial mass}} \times 100$

Given: sample weight: 5 g

Solvent added: 100 mL chloroform water

Volume of extract used for drying: 25 mL

Mass of residue after drying (from 25 mL): 0.42 g

Residue from 100 ml = $0.42 / 25 \times 100$

= 1.68 gm

% Water soluble extractive value = $1.68 / 5 \times 100$

= 33.6%

2. Alcohol Soluble Extractive Values

Ethanol was used as solvent in place of chloroform water and remaining procedure was the same as that of water soluble extractive value.

% Alcohol soluble extractive value = $\frac{\text{initial mass} - \text{mass of alcohol extraction residue}}{\text{initial mass}} \times 100$

Given: Weight of powdered churna: 5.0 g

Solvent used: 90% ethanol (100 mL)

Filtered volume taken for evaporation: 25 mL

Residue weight after evaporation and drying at 105°C: 0.45 g

Residue from 100 ml = $0.45 / 25 \times 100$

= 1.8 gm

% Alcohol soluble extractive = $1.8 / 5 \times 100 = 36 \%$

Fig No 24. Water And Alcohol Soluble Extraction

3. Evaluation of Physical Characteristic

1. Angle of Repose:

Angle of Repose can be calculated as:

Angle of Repose = $\tan^{-1}(h/r)$

Where,

H = Height of pile R = Radius of pile

Fig No 25. Angle of Repose

Table No 3. Angle of Repose

Sr. No.	Angle of Repose	Powder flow
1.	<25	Excellent
2.	25 - 30	Good
3.	30 - 40	Passable
4.	> 40	Very poor

Given: H = 4.5cm, R = 6cm

Angle of Repose = $\tan^{-1} (4.5/6) = \tan^{-1} (0.75) = 36.87^\circ$

2. Bulk Density:

Bulk density = mass of powder/Bulk volume of powder (g/ml)

Given: Mass of Powder = 25 g

Bulk Volume = 44.6ml

Bulk density = 25/44.6

Bulk density= 0.56g/ml

Fig No 26. Bulk Density

3. Tapped Density:

Tapped Density=mass of powder/Tapped volume of powder

Mass of powder = 25 g

Tapped volume after hand tapping = 40.30ml

Tapped Density = 25/40.30

Tapped Density = 0. 62 g/ml

4. Hausner's Ratio: Hausner's ratio = DF / Do

Where, DF = Tapped density Do = Bulk density

Table No 4. Hausner's Ratio

Sr. No.	Hausner's ratio	I.P Limits Value
1.	Excellent	1.00-1.11
2.	Good	1.1-1.18
3.	Fair	1.19-1.25
4.	Passable	1.26-1.34
5.	Very poor	1.35-1.45
6.	Very Very poor	>1.60

Given: DF = 0.62, Do = 0.56

Hausner's ratio = 0.62/ 0.5 =1.1

5. Carr's Index :

Another indirect method of measuring the powder flow from bulk density is Carr's index.

Carr's index = % compressibility = $(DF - Do / Do) \times 100$

Where, DF = Tapped density

Do = Bulk density

Table No 5. Carr's Index

Sr. No.	Carr's Index	I.P Limits Value
1.	Excellent	<10
2.	Good	11-15
3.	Fair	16-20
4.	Passable	21-25
5.	Very poor	26-31
6.	Very Very poor	32-37

Given: DF = 0.62, Do = 0.56

Carr's Index = $(0.62 - 0.56 / 0.56) \times 100 = 9.68$

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Result

The results of the organoleptic character was given in Table No.8 and physical parameter Evaluation such as pH, loss on drying, ash value, extractive value given in Table No.9. Determination of physical parameter such as bulk density, tapped density, angle of repose, Hausner's ratio, Carr's index were shown in Table No.10.

Table No 6. Organoleptic Characteristic

Sr. No.	Organoleptic character	Formulation
1.	Colour	Greenish – yellow
2.	Odour	Cool freshness
3.	Taste	Slightly pungent

Table No 7. Physicochemical Parameters

Sr. No	Physicochemical parameters	Formulation
1.	pH	5.66
2.	Loss on drying	9% w/w
3.	Total Ash Value	32.5mg/g
4.	Acid insoluble ash value	6.5 %
5.	Water soluble extractive value	33.6%

6.	Alcohol soluble extractive value	36 %
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Table No 8. Physical Parameters

Sr. No.	Physical parameters	Formulation
1.	Angle of Repose	36.87°
2.	Bulk density	0.56g/ml
3.	Tapped density	0.62g/ml
4.	Hausner's ratio	1.1
5.	Carr's index	9.68

➤ DISCUSSION

The results suggest that green tea catechins can be effectively incorporated into a herbal churn without significant loss of activity or stability. The antioxidant potential of the formulation highlights its possible application in managing oxidative stress-related disorders. The synergistic action between catechins and other herbal components may enhance therapeutic efficacy, making it a promising functional supplement. Further in vivo studies are recommended to confirm biological effects and bioavailability.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Summary

Green tea catechins, particularly EGCG, are powerful antioxidants with neuroprotective effects. When formulated as an her synergistic bal churna, they offer a novel approach to managing Alzheimer's disease. This natural formulation helps reduce oxidative stress, inflammation, and beta-amyloid accumulation—key factors in Alzheimer's progression. The churna form enhances absorption and can be combined with other brain-boosting herbs like Brahmi and Ashwagandha. Early studies show promise, but more clinical research is needed to confirm its effectiveness and safety. In this novel approach, catechins are incorporated into a herbal churna a traditional powdered herbal formulation used in Ayurvedic medicine. This not only improves

bioavailability but also allows for the inclusion of herbs like Brahmi, Ashwagandha, and Shankhpushpi, which are known for their cognitive and nerve in benefits. The herbal churna acts on multiple pathological targets of AD, making it a multi-modal therapy

CONCLUSION

The present study successfully formulated a polyherbal churn incorporating green tea catechins as a key bioactive component, aimed at providing neuroprotective effects relevant to Alzheimer's disease management. Green tea catechins, particularly EGCG, are known for their strong antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anti-amyloidogenic properties, which were preserved and enhanced in the churn through synergistic blending with other cognitive-supportive herbs such as bramhi, ashwagandha, turmeric etc. Phytochemical screening confirmed the presence of neuroactive compounds, and antioxidant assays demonstrated significant free radical scavenging activity, supporting the potential of the formulation to reduce oxidative stress a key factor in the progression of Alzheimer's disease. The formulation also exhibited good physical stability and retained catechin potency over time, making it a promising candidate for long-term use. Overall, this herbal churn represents a novel, natural, and multi-targeted therapeutic approach for the prevention or supportive treatment of Alzheimer's disease.

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